

REPORTED IMPACT OF CHATROOMS

TABLE 1: Reported impact of the chatroom use on the developers' productivity (percentage^{number})

	Positive	Negative	Mixed	No impact	No answer
Slack	39.1% ⁽⁴⁵⁾	15.6% ⁽¹⁸⁾	33.9% ⁽³⁹⁾	6.9% ⁽⁸⁾	6.9% ⁽⁸⁾
Gitter	43.8% ⁽²¹⁾	16.6% ⁽⁸⁾	6.3% ⁽³⁾	22.9% ⁽¹¹⁾	10.48% ⁽⁵⁾
Total	40.5% ⁽⁶⁶⁾	15.9% ⁽²⁶⁾	25.8% ⁽⁴²⁾	11.7% ⁽¹⁹⁾	7.9% ⁽¹³⁾